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Automatic Privacy Query Updation for Moving Objects

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Abstract Preventing moving objects location tracking from intruders. In recent years moving object databases have gained much interest due to the advances in mobile communications and positioning technologies. To provide security to moving object needs monitoring. Monitoring moving objects have two fundamental issues like efficiency and privacy. This paper proposes an efficient algorithm for finding good anonymization group for given moving objects (MOB) with respect to its quasi-identifier (QID) and dynamic query updation. To address the efficiency and privacy issues we are using a new technique which updates the query of the MOB in the base stations automatically. Furthermore, by using the location management method we are solving the issues of location updating.

Keywords-*Spatial databases, location-Updates, Mobility Management, mobile applications.*

Introduction

Location awareness, the ability to determine geographical position, is an emerging technology with both significant benefits and important privacy implications for users of mobile devices. We are on the cusp of a new era in technology where the location of computing and communications devices can be determined accurately and inexpensively. Now-a-days almost all the people are using location aware devices, e.g., GPSenabled cell

phones and PDA's location sensors and active RFID tags. This enables monitoring of moving objects and real-time analysis of their motion patterns, as well as the collection of the traces left by these moving objects [1].

To provide secrecy to the moving object location we need to update the location information along with the query of that moving object. We can do the updation of the

moving object with the help of the location management method. Time-based Location Management method forms two phases: Location Update (LU) and paging (P) [2]. When we are working with moving objects location information we need to monitor moving objects time to time so that location information should be updated and can provide security to the moving object.

Existing works has problem with dynamic query update, this paper overcomes that problem by using the dynamic query updation algorithm and location management method. A mobile informs the base station (BS) of its location during a Location Update operation at the same time BS will get the query information from the MOB. The system stores this information of a mobile terminal (MT) when the query is set and in exchange it sends the code of the query generated by the system with the MT call. There are very few studies on continuous query monitoring are focused on location updates.

Two commonly used updating approaches are periodic update and deviation update [5], [6], [7], [8]. We are using the quasiidentifier for providing good anonymity to the moving objects. It is very likely that various moving objects have different quasi-identifiers and this should be taken into account in modeling adversarial knowledge. Hence the concept of quasi-identifier must be modeled subjectively, on an individual basis. Figure 1(a) shows a moving object database. Each row represents the trajectory of a moving object (MOB) and shows the position of the MOB at different times, in a rectangular grid. The original identities (say $I1$, $I2$, $I3$) of the

individuals have been suppressed and have been replaced by MOB ids $O1$, $O2$, $O3$. For the three individuals $I1$, $I2$ and $I3$, a possible scenario is that an adversary knows the location of $I1$ at time point $t1$, and that of $I2$ and $I3$ at $t2$. In this paper, we study the problem of privacy-preserving publishing of a moving objects database. Our goal is to anonymize the trajectories so that no MOB can be reidentified by matching its quasi-identifier with the published dataset. The main issue in anonymizing MOB data is that, due to the fact that different objects may have different QIDs, anonymization groups associated with different objects may not be disjoint, as illustrated below. **Example 1:** Consider the trajectories in Figure 1(a) and illustrated in Figure 1(c). Let $k = 2$ and $QID(O1) = \{t1\}$, $QID(O2) = QID(O3) = \{t2\}$. Intuitively the best (w.r.t. information loss) anonymization group for $O1$ w.r.t. its QID $\{t1\}$ is $AS(O1) = \{O1, O2\}$. This is illustrated in Figure 1(c) with a dark rectangle. This means in the anonymized database we assign the region $[(1, 2), (2, 3)]$ to $O1$ and $O2$ at time $t1$.

The best anonymization group for $O2$ as well as for $O3$ w.r.t. their QID $\{t2\}$ is $\{O2, O3\}$. Thus, in the anonymized database, $O2$ and $O3$ will both be assigned to the common region $[(2, 6), (3, 7)]$ (the second dark rectangle) at time $t2$. Clearly, the anonymization groups of $O1$ and $O2$ overlap. Due to this fact providing a robust and sound definition of k -anonymity in the case of MOD is challenging. The most obvious way of defining k -anonymity is to say that a given object must be indistinguishable from all the objects in

its own anonymization group for each timestamp in its own QID. According to this definition the database in Figure 1(b) is 2-anonymous and thus “safe”. This obvious definition of k -anonymity still suffers privacy breaches. Indeed, due the fact that anonymization groups may not be disjoint, it is possible that by combining overlapping anonymization groups, some moving objects may be uniquely identified, as explained next. Recall the previous example. There, I_1 and I_2 are in the same anonymization group (i.e., have the same generalized location) at time point t_1 (i.e., the QID of I_1), while I_2 and I_3 are in the same anonymization group at time point t_2 (i.e., the QID of I_2 and I_3). However, when the adversary tries to map the three MOBs O_1, O_2, O_3 to the three individuals I_1, I_2, I_3 , with the adversary knowledge of QID values of these three MOBs, he can infer that I_1 must be mapped to either O_1 or O_2 , while I_2 (and I_3) should be mapped to either O_2 or O_3 . If I_1 is mapped to O_2 , we cannot find a consistent assignment for I_2, I_3 . As a result, the adversary can conclude that O_1 must map to I_1 .

Thus, we need a more sophisticated definition of k -anonymity to avoid privacy breaches in the case of moving object databases.

Fig 1: Example MOB Database (assuming $QID(O_1) = \{t_1\}$, $QID(O_2) = QID(O_3) = \{t_2\}$): (a) original database; (b) a 2-anonymity scheme that is not safe, and (c) its graphical representation.

The theme of this paper is to update the query of MOB for preventing moving object from tracking to do so we have to monitor the moving object which needs to overcome the fundamental issues of monitoring [4].

II. RELATED WORKS

Existing work on preventing of spatiotemporal moving objects location from tracking has been mainly conducted in the context of location based services (LBS). In this context a trusted server is usually in charge of handling users’ requests and passing them on the service providers, and the general goal is to provide the service on-the-fly without threatening the anonymity of the user requiring the service. The trusted server uses spatial-cloaking (i.e., space generalization) to make the request sent from a user indistinguishable from $k-1$ other requests [11]. Based on this idea a system that supports different queries and various anonymization requirements was developed in [10] [9]. Early work assumed a static data set and focused on efficient access methods (e.g., R-tree [12]) and query evaluation algorithms (e.g., [13], [14]). Recently, a lot

of attention has been paid to moving-object databases, where data objects or queries or both of them move.

Assuming that object movement trajectories are known a priori, Saltenis et al. [15] proposed the Time-Parameterized R-tree (TPR-tree) for indexing moving objects, where the location of a moving object is represented by a linear function of time. Benetis et al. [16] developed query evaluation algorithms for NN and reverse NN search based on the TPR-tree. Tao et al. [17] optimized the performance of the TPR-tree and extended it to the *TPR-tree*. Chon et al. [18] studied range and kNN queries based on a grid model. Patel et al. [19] proposed a novel index structure called STRIPES using a dual transformation technique.

The work on monitoring continuous spatial queries can be classified into two categories. The first category assumes that the movement trajectories are known. Continuous kNN monitoring has been investigated for moving queries over stationary objects [20] and linearly moving objects [21], [22]. Iwerks et al. [21] extended to monitor distance semijoins for two linearly moving data sets [23]. However, as pointed out in [24], the known-trajectory assumption does not hold for many application scenarios (e.g., the velocity of a car changes frequently on road). The second category does not make any assumption on object movement patterns. Xu et al. [25] and Zhang et al. [26] suggested returning to the client both the query result and its validity scope where the result remains the same. As such, the query is reevaluated only when the query exits the validity scope. However, their solutions work for stationary objects only. For continuous monitoring of moving objects, the prevailing approach is periodic reevaluation of queries [27], [28], [29], [30]. Prabhakar et al. [29] proposed the Q-index, which indexes queries using an R-tree-like structure. At each evaluation step, only those objects that have moved since the previous evaluation step are evaluated on the Q-index. While this study is limited to range queries, Mokbel et al. [28] proposed a scalable incremental hash-based algorithm (SINA) for range and kNN queries. SINA indexes both queries and objects, and achieves scalability by employing shared execution and incremental evaluation of continuous queries [28], [31]. Kalashnikov et al. and Yu et al. suggested grid-based in memory structures for object and query indexes to speed up reevaluation process of range queries [32] and kNN queries [30]. Access methods to support frequent location updates of moving objects have also been investigated [27], [33]. Our study falls into this category but distinguishes itself from existing studies with a comprehensive framework focusing on location update.

Uncertainty and privacy issues have been recently studied in moving object monitoring. To protect location privacy, various cloaking or anonymizing techniques have been proposed to hide the client’s actual location. Among them are the spatiotemporal cloaking [34], the Clique-Cloak [35], [36], the Casper anonymizer [37], *hilbASR* [38], [39],

and peer-to-peer cloaking [40], [41]. In spatiotemporal cloaking, or each location update, the server divides the space recursively in a quad-tree-like format till a suitable subspace is found to cloak the updated location. The CliqueCloak algorithm constructs a clique graph to combine some clients who can share the same cloaked spatial area. The Casper anonymizer is associated with a query processor to ensure that the anonymized area returns the same query result as the actual location. In *hilbASR*, all user locations are sorted by Hilbert space-filling curve ordering, and then, every k users are grouped together in this order. Besides, location cloaking, *pseudonym*, *dummy*, and *transformation* were also proposed for privacy preservation. Pseudonym decouples the mapping between the user identity and the location so that an untrusted server only receives the location without the user identity [42], [43]. Dummy generates fake user locations (called dummies) and mixes them together with the genuine user location into the request [44], [45], [46]. Transformation utilizes certain one-way spatial transformations (e.g., a space filling curve) to map the query space to another space and resolves query blindly in the transformed space [47]. As for location uncertainty, a common model for characterizing the uncertainty of an object is a closed region with a predefined probability distribution of this object in the region. Based on this probabilistic model, query processing and indexing algorithms have been proposed to evaluate probabilistic range queries [48], [37] and kNN queries [49].

While in these studies, the objects are uncertain, the queries themselves are still certain. Chen and Cheng extended the probabilistic processing to more general cases where the queries are also uncertain [50]. Our study, on the other hand, addresses the continuous monitoring issue. By adopting the notion of “safe region,” the frequency of query reevaluation on uncertain location information is reduced, and hence, the system efficiency and scalability are improved.

Distributed approaches have been investigated to monitor continuous range queries [51], [52] and continuous kNN queries [53]. The main idea is to shift some load from the server to the mobile clients. Monitoring queries have also been studied for distributed Internet databases [54], data streams [55], and sensor databases [56]. However, these studies are not applicable to monitoring of moving objects, where a two-dimensional space is assumed.

A location update is used to inform the network of a mobile device’s location. This requires the device to register its new location with the current base station, to allow the forwarding of incoming calls. Each location update is a costly exercise, involving the use of cellular network bandwidth and core network communication; including the modification of location databases [AMH+99]. A wide variety of schemes have hence been proposed to reduce the number of location update messages required by a device in a cellular network. Location update schemes are often partitioned into the categories of static and dynamic [BNIM95, AMH+99, WL00,

ADM98]. Static schemes offer a lower level of cost reduction but reduced computational complexity. Dynamic schemes adjust location update frequency per user and are hence able to achieve better results, while requiring a higher degree of computational overhead. Dynamic location update schemes allow per-user parameterisation of the location update frequency. These account for the dynamic behaviour of users and may result in lower location management costs than static schemes. Unlike static location management strategies, a location update may be performed from any cell in the network, taking into consideration the call arrival and mobility patterns of the user. Dynamic location update properties varies as per the schemes, the following are the schemes we have in:

- Threshold-based Scheme
- Time-based Scheme
- Movement-based Scheme
- Distance-based Scheme
- Profile based and adaptive

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Problem Definition

The existing system proposes that the server will not automatically update the Query of the mobile object (MO) as it is updating the location when the mobile is moving from one base station (BS) to the other. The Problem with the existing system is that the updation of MO query is not happening when the MO moves to the other BS’s. In the proposed system we are introducing an algorithm along with the anonymity which will help the BS’s to identify the query of the MO and provide security as per the query of MO.

B. Moving Object Concealment

A basic building block for devising any notion of anonymity is a notion of indistinguishability. Let D^* be a distorted version of a MOD D . We say that two MOBs O, O' are indistinguishable in D^* at time t provided that $D^*(O, t) = D^*(O', t)$, i.e., both are assigned to the same region in D^* .

The most obvious way of defining k -anonymity is the following: a distorted version D^* of a MOD D satisfies k -anonymity provided: for every MOB O in D , $\exists k - 1$ other distinct MOBs $O_1 \dots O_{k-1}$ in D^* : $\forall t \in \text{QID}(O)$, O is indistinguishable from each of O_1, \dots, O_{k-1} at time t . Consider the trajectories in Figure 1(a) and illustrated in Figure 1(c). Let $k = 2$ and $\text{QID}(O_1) = \{t_1\}$, $\text{QID}(O_2) = \text{QID}(O_3) = \{t_2\}$. Intuitively the best (w.r.t. information loss) anonymization group for O_1 w.r.t. its QID $\{t_1\}$ is $\text{AS}(O_1) = \{O_1, O_2\}$. This is illustrated in Figure 1(c) with a dark rectangle. This means in the anonymized database we assign the region $[(1, 2), (2, 3)]$ to O_1 and O_2 at time t_1 . The best anonymization group for O_2 as well as for O_3 w.r.t. their QID $\{t_2\}$ is $\{O_2, O_3\}$. Thus, in the anonymized database, O_2 and O_3 will both be assigned to the common region $[(2, 6), (3, 7)]$ (the second dark rectangle) at time t_2 . Clearly, the anonymization groups of O_1 and O_2

overlap... It is easy to see that the distorted database D^* in Figure 1(b) satisfies this notion.

Yet, we saw that privacy can be breached in this case. We next formalize the attack model employed by the adversary and use it to show how privacy is breached. The first notion we introduce is an attack graph.

Definition 1 (Attack Graph): An attack graph associated with a MOD D and its distorted version D^* is a bipartite graph G consisting of nodes for every individual I in D (called I -nodes) and nodes for every MOB id O (called O -nodes) in the published database D^* . G contains an edge (I, O) iff $D(O, t) \subseteq D^*(O, t), \forall t \in \text{QID}(I)$.

An assignment of individuals to MOB is consistent provided there exists a perfect matching in the bipartite graph G . In our running example, consider the distorted database shown in Figure 1(b): the corresponding attack graph is shown in Figure 2(a). It is obvious that the edge (I_1, O_1) must be a part of every perfect matching. Thus, by constructing the attack graph an attacker may easily conclude that MOB O_1 can be re-identified as I_1 .

One of the key shortcomings in the straightforward definition of k -anonymity given above is that while it ensures

Fig 2: Attack graphs for different anonymization schemes: (a) for D^* in Figure 1(b); (b) for a hypothetical database D^* satisfying modified definition of k -anonymity.

every I -node corresponding to an individual has at least k -neighbors, it does not have any restriction on the degree of the O -nodes. What if we required that in addition, every O -node must have degree at least k ? Suppose we say that a distorted database is k -anonymous provided in the corresponding attack graph, every I -node as well as every O -node has degree $\geq k$. Figure 2(b) shows a possible attack graph that satisfies this condition. In this graph, every I -node and every O -node has degree 2 or more. Yet, O_5 can be successfully re-identified as I_5 as follows. Suppose O_5 is instead assigned to I_2 , to which it is adjacent as well. Then it is easy to see that no I -node can be assigned to one of O_1, O_2 . Thus, the edge (I_2, O_5) cannot be a part of any perfect matching. Thus, this edge can be pruned, leaving I_5 as the only I -node to which O_5 can be assigned.

Definition 2 (Attack Model). The attacker first constructs an attack graph associated with the published distorted version of D and the known QIDs as described in **Definition 1**. Then, he repeats the following operation until there is no change to the graph:

1. Identify an edge e that cannot be part of any perfect matching.
2. Prune the edge e .

Next, we propose a notation of k -anonymity, which guarantees there exists a perfect matching for any arbitrary node in the attack graph.

Definition 3 (k -anonymity). Let D be a MOD and D^* its distorted version. Let G be the attack graph w.r.t. D, D^* , given a set of QIDs for the MOB in D . Then D^* satisfies the k -anonymity condition provided: (i) every I -node in G has degree k or more; and (ii) G is symmetric, i.e., whenever G contains an edge (I_i, O_j) , it also contains the edge (I_j, O_i) .

An immediate observation is that in an attack graph that satisfies the above conditions, every O -node will have degree k or more as well. We call a distorted database D^* k -anonymous if it satisfies Definition 3.

C. Dynamic Query updation algorithm

Algorithm

1. **while** receiving a request **do**
2. **if** the request is to register query q **then**
3. evaluate q ;
4. generate unique query id ;
5. compute its quarantine area and insert it into the query index;
6. return the results to the application server;
7. return unique query id to the mobile terminal;
8. update the changed safe regions of objects and the query updation through unique id ;
9. **else if** the request is to deregister query q **then**
10. remove q from the query index;
11. **else if** the request is a location update from object p **then**
12. determine the set of affected queries;
13. **for each** affected query q_i **do**
14. reevaluate q_i ;
15. update the results to the application server;
16. recompute its quarantine area and update the query index;
17. update the safe region of p ;

Fig 3: Algorithm for the automatic updation of Query and Location of MOB

D. Design Analyses

Fig 4: Step by step process of the Query/location updation of MOB

The data i.e, request will be generated by the MT then the request will be carried to the server by the BS. In this scenario BS acts as an interface, query varies from user to user of the MT sometimes it may be about location, sometimes it may be about the privacy, the algorithm in Fig 3 explains that to process the query regarding privacy it processes two queries one is location and the another one is privacy, because to provide privacy to the MOB / MT the server should know its location or the BS it is connected to. The query processor in the server processes the query and generates query index, object index and unique id. Location update manages updates the location every time when ever the object moves from one location to the other and sets the location safe region only when the MOB moves out of the BS range. Unique id is send to the MOB/MT, whenever the object moves out of the range simultaneously along with the location updation the privacy will be provided to the MOB/MT.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes an algorithm for automatic privacy query updation along with the location updation process. This is the first technique which address about the issue of the autotmatic privacy query updation. Furthermore, this algorithm is best in providing privacy automatically even when the mobile terminal moves to other BS.

As for future work, we plan to work on multiple queries.

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